

BC-SIM-TR-035

SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04 Test Report

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Approvation

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

This document will briefly report the results of the tests performed during the Instrument Checkout (ICO) # 04 for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM (SIMBIO-SYS) whose details are reported in [RD.1].

1.2. Reference document

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-PL-006_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_04_Test_Summary_Issue1_Rev0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204)
- [RD.2] BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow_v2,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)
- [RD.3] BC-SIM-TR-032_-_HRIC_ICO#04_report,
[10.5281/zenodo.8366034](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366034)
- [RD.4] BC-SIM-TR-031_-_STC_ICO#04_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208)
- [RD.5] BC-SIM-TR-033_-_VIHI_ICO#04_report
- [RD.6] BC-SIM-TR-034_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Interchannel_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.8366159](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366159)
- [RD.7] SIMBIO-SYS Instrument CheckOut #03 Test Report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/201](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/201)
- [RD.8] BC-SIM-TN-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP_update_after_ICO#02,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162)
- [RD.9] BC-SIM-TR-005_-_SIMBIO-SYS_NECP_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/42](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/42)

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[RD.10] BC-SIM-TR-010_-_SIMBIO-SYS_deltaNECP_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/83](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/83)

[RD.11] BC-SIM-TR-015_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#01_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/98](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/98)

1.3. Acronyms

APID	Application Process IDentifier
ASW	Application SoftWare
CM	Color Mode
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ICO	Instrument Checkout
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
SSMM	Solid State Mass Memory
STC	STereo imaging Channel
S/C	Space-Craft
TC	TeleCommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler

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TM	Telemetry
VIHI	VIisible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1.4. Document format and repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.2] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5. Document organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – ICO#04 objectives, with a brief description of the performance and inter-channel tests executed.
- Section 3 – ICO#04 implementation, with a brief description of the Flight Operation Procedures (FOPs) and Payload Direct Operation Requests (PDORs) used to perform the required tests and a discussion on the obtained results. More details are reported in each channel report ([RD.3], [RD.4] and [RD.5]) and in the interference test report ([RD.6]).

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2. ICO#04 Objective

The scope of the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04 was to verify the health status of the instrument at channel level 2 years after launch. To do this, three kinds of tests were defined (see [RD.1] for details):

1. **Functional Tests**, to verify the functionality of all the SIMBIO-SYS units (i.e., ME, HRIC, STC, and VIHI) and their components (e.g., TECs, Detectors, etc.).
2. **Performance Tests**, to monitor the evolution of the performance of all the SIMBIO-SYS channels (i.e., HRIC, STC, and VIHI) with respect to the results obtained during the on-ground calibration campaign and the tests performed during the Cruise.
3. **Interchannel Tests**, to evaluate if and how the cameras (i.e., HRIC and STC) detector reset fluctuations (see Open Issue #10 in [RD.7]) change with respect to the Repetition Time parameter and if the operativity of the VIHI channel influences or not such a fluctuation.

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3. Test Implementation

The SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04 tests have been executed December 14th, 2020. In this document, after a brief introduction on the foreseen tests, their results are summarized evidencing eventual issues, more deeply discussed in referenced Technical Notes ([RD.3], [RD.4], [RD.5] and [RD.6]).

All tests described in the following sections have been executed by means of proper FOPs, On-Board Control Procedures (OBCPs), and PDORs whose description can be found in [RD.1]. All the tests used the last version of SIBIOSYS FOPs (detailed in [RD.8]).

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3.1. SIMBIO-SYS Functional Tests

3.1.1. HRIC Functional Test

3.1.1.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to check the channel functionality and its capability to perform some science acquisitions.

3.1.1.2. Results and discussion

The test has been executed without errors, but the not nominal SIMBIO-SYS thermal conditions affected the evaluation of the expected (and already seen in previous ICOs) detector reset level fluctuation.

More details on the test results can be found in [RD.3].

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3.1.2. STC Functional Test

3.1.2.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to check the functionality of the channel units and the capability to perform some science acquisitions.

3.1.2.2. Results and discussion

The test has been executed as expected confirming the channel functionality **but the not nominal SIMBIO-SYS thermal conditions affected the evaluation of the Dark Current (DC) measurement.** More details on the test results can be found in [RD.4].

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3.2. SIMBIO-SYS Performance Tests

3.2.1. HRIC Performance Test

3.2.1.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to perform several science acquisitions to evaluate the channel Dark Current (DC) performance after 2 years from launch.

3.2.1.2. Results and discussion

The test was executed **with no errors**. The **obtained data**, once reduced by the scientific team, **present some differences with respect to the previous ICOs due to the not nominal thermal environment state**. More details on the test results can be found in [RD.3].

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3.2.2. STC Performance Test

3.2.2.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to perform several science acquisitions to evaluate the channel DC performance after 2 years from launch.

3.2.2.2. Results and discussion

As per the HRIC channel, **the obtained data demonstrate the channel performances are in line with what expected.** The test demonstrates the **Mitigate strategy** efficiency: a limited number of acquisitions of WinX before the Color Mode (CM) ones guarantee to avoid the peak effect reducing the DC additive level. More details on the test results can be found in [RD.4].

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3.2.3. VIHI Internal Calibration

3.2.3.1. Scope

The scope of this test was to repeat the test done during the ICO#03 with a verification of the VIHI functional capability together with the LED internal calibration performance.

3.2.3.2. Results and discussion

The test failed its execution due to a critical error occurred at the beginning of the science acquisition and so the VIHI performance couldn't be verified. In addition, the channel became un-responsive and so it was powered-off affecting following interference test. More details on the test results can be found [RD.5].

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3.3. SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Tests

3.3.1. SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test

3.3.1.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if and how the cameras (i.e., HRIC and STC) detector reset fluctuations depends on the change with respect to the RT parameter and on the parallel operativity of the VIHI channel.

3.3.1.2. Results and discussion

As reported in 3.2.3.2, **the test partially failed** due to the VIHI issue (i.e., it has not possible to verify if VIHI operativity affects the cameras detector fluctuations issue).

Apart from the VIHI issue, **the test demonstrates that HRIC operativity affect STC detector fluctuation.** In any case, **the results have been affected by the not nominal SIMBIO-SYS thermal conditions.** More details can be found in [RD.6].

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4. Conclusions

4.1. Summary

During the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04, some tests have been executed to evaluate the instrument's health status and the evolution of its performance after 2 years cruise. With these tests, all the units (i.e., ME, HRIC, STC, and VIHI) have operated nominally, but with some problem in the results interpretation due to **the not nominal SIMBIO-SYS thermal conditions**.

4.2. Open issues

During the execution of the ICO#04 tests, the following **Events** raised:

#	Name	Description	Occurrence	Connected ARs
1	SIMBIO-SYS Thermal issue	SIMBIO-SYS was not in the nominal thermal conditions due to the not activation of S/C redundant heater	All test	-
2	VIHI Science TC failure	VIHI science TC rejected by PE due to EOP/EOR not received during	VIHI Performance Test	BC_SC-150

Table 1: List of anomalous Events occurred during ICO#04.

The status of the **Issues** at the end of ICO#04 phase is reported in following table:

#	Name	Status at the end of the ICO#04
1	SHUTTER	Open: (see [RD.9]) the error on the PE-ME SpW is not managed in the present version of the ME ASW but it will be fixed in the next one. The issue will be checked and resolved after the ME ASW update.
2	ME-GRANULARITY	Open: (see [RD.10]) it has been found that the ME granularity managing TC execution could be modified by the Repetition Time (RT) parameter of a Science TC determining that some TC can be accepted but not executed (see section 4.2 of [RD.11]).
3	ACK MISSING	Open: (see [RD.10]) it is understood that in the case of Science on Science mode (i.e., a Science or STOP TC is sent while the channel is already in Science mode) the new TC is accepted

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		immediately (i.e., ACK sent) and it should be executed at the end of the RT of the previous one. If during this delay one or more additive TCs occurred, all of them are immediately accepted (i.e., ACKs sent) but only the last one is executed and even the "waiting one" is lost without any indication of that (i.e., no TM(1,8) received for all the TCs apart the last one that is executed).
4	PACKET SORTING	Open: (see [RD.10]) some science packets presented a wrong time tag determining a bad frame reconstruction. The reason for this issue is still under study.
5	LFB	Open: Both HRIC and STC channels reports a not expected fluctuation of the detector reset level (around the 0.1% of the dynamical range).
6	STC-RT limits	Open: There is a limit in the DB between 30 and 4000 but STC-RT commanded was not in line with ASW limits (2460 raw).
7	LFB-Interference	Open: While operating in parallel, the LFB of the two cameras change in terms of amplitude and frequency. More tests are necessary to understand the effect.
8	VIHI Science TC failure	Closed: In VIHI TC Science the Dark Acquisition and Dark Subtraction flag cannot be used in parallel.

Table 2: List of Issues after ICO#04.